

ClimBurst: a Novel Method to Detect Climatological Anomalies over Time and Space

Audrey Brouillet^{1,2*}, Guillaume Coulaud³, Dennis Shasha⁴, Reza Akbarinia⁵,
Florent Massegla⁵

¹Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), Member of the Leibniz Association, PO Box 60
12 03, 14412 Potsdam, Germany

²ESPACE-DEV, Université Montpellier, IRD, Université Guyane, Université Réunion, Université Antilles,
Montpellier, France

³University of Montpellier, Inria, CNRS, LIRMM

⁴Courant Institute of Mathematical Sciences, New York University

⁵Inria, University of Montpellier, CNRS, LIRMM

Key Points:

- A new method *ClimBurst* is described that can detect climate bursts (anomalies) without prior knowledge of their duration nor spatial extent;
- Connected component analysis applied to detected bursts allows us to track how anomalies propagate and connect in time and space;
- As a case study, *ClimBurst* detects SST hot anomalies and captures their increased intensity in magnitude, frequency, duration and spatial extent.

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Corresponding author: Audrey Brouillet, audrey.brouillet@pik-potsdam.de

Abstract

Detecting abnormal climate events across temporal and spatial scales is crucial to the understanding of local and regional climate trends. Existing methods often depend on prior knowledge about the timing, location, or duration of such events, limiting their versatility. This study introduces *ClimBurst*, an approach to detect climate bursts (unusually high or low values of climate variables) without prior assumptions about their temporal duration. *ClimBurst* offers the ability to: (i) identify climate bursts of any duration within the time series of single locations, (ii) link climate bursts across neighboring locations, and (iii) analyze the spatio-temporal propagation of these anomalies. Applying *ClimBurst* to Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data from the Mediterranean Sea (1960–2021) shows some detected hot bursts and anomalies coincide in time with known severe marine heatwaves. *ClimBurst* also shows how detected hot (cold) bursts are spatio-temporally connected and this connected bursts have increased (decreased) in duration, intensity, spatial extent and frequency historically.

Plain Language Summary

Detecting abnormal climate events is crucial for understanding, predicting, and managing climate risks. However, most existing methods require prior knowledge about when and where to search for these events, limiting their effectiveness. In this study, we introduce *ClimBurst*, a new method to identify climate-related anomalies that does not require any prior information about their duration or spatial extent. We propose computing climate bursts to detect abnormal seasonal activity. The *ClimBurst* approach can detect anomalies at any time scale. The approach also compares anomalies at neighboring locations enabling the tracking of events across time and space. We apply our method on Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data from the Mediterranean Sea between 1960 and 2021, where we detect particularly strong warm anomalies that can last from a few days to a few months over a few kilometers to hundreds, such as the 2015 marine heatwave. Our results reveal a noticeable increase in the frequency, magnitude and the spatial extent of these hot anomalies over time. Researchers and practitioners can use *ClimBurst* to detect and study climate anomalies, providing a basis for event attribution and long-term trend analysis.

1 Introduction

Climate researchers have identified the detection of extreme climate events and related anomalies as a topic requiring extensive research (Sillmann et al., 2017). Anomalous events can significantly affect various sectors including agriculture (Beillouin et al., 2020; Vogel et al., 2019), water availability (Schilling et al., 2020; Vinke et al., 2017) and health (Alcayna et al., 2022; Charlson et al., 2021; Javadinejad et al., 2020; Bell et al., 2018). To cite a few recent examples from the literature of related studies, authors of (Beillouin et al., 2020) use agricultural yield and climate data from 17 European countries to demonstrate that negative yields result from extremes in temperature and precipitation. In (Alcayna et al., 2022), the authors conducted a scoping review of the relationship between climate-sensitive infectious diseases and climate extremes. In particular, they show an association between water-borne diseases and extremes. These two examples illustrate the necessity of accurately detecting and anticipating extreme events.

Extreme weather and climate events are usually defined as “discrete episodes of extreme weather or unusual climate conditions, often associated with deleterious impacts on society or natural systems, defined using some metric to characterize either the meteorological characteristics of the event or the consequent impacts” (Stott et al., 2016). As human-driven greenhouse gas emissions have led to global warming that results in more frequent and intensified extreme events (Gulev et al., 2021), it has become crucial

68 to reliably detect and study such possible risks (Chen et al., 2018). Many previous stud-
69 ies have developed related detection approaches using statistical and dynamic modeling.
70 One common way to characterize and investigate climate-related anomalies is, for instance,
71 the use of standardized indexes. These indexes transform raw observations into normal-
72 ized data (mostly relative to their means) making them easier to interpret. For instance,
73 the Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI) quantifies observed precipitation as a stan-
74 dardized departure from a selected probability distribution function that models the raw
75 precipitation data (Thomas B. McKee & Kleist, 1993; Tsakiris & Vangelis, 2005). Quan-
76 titatively, SPI values are the number of standard deviations by which the observed anomaly
77 deviates from the long-term mean. The SPI is usually created using monthly input val-
78 ues and for differing periods from 1 to 36 months. A large number of standardized in-
79 dexes to investigate climate-related anomalies (droughts, floods, vegetation anomalies,
80 combined temperature-precipitation) have now been developed and adapted from this
81 original index (Şen, 2024). Abrupt or extreme climate events can also be identified in
82 spatio-temporal data by using edge detectors (Bathiany et al., 2020). Other approaches
83 identify anomalous events using clustering, particularly when focusing on individual days
84 and point anomalies (Ramachandra et al., 2016; Zscheischler et al., 2013).

85 Some tools identify climate extremes by computing the percentile of each month-
86 day-year date for each measure (e.g. temperature) relative to the same month-day in other
87 years. If the percentile for a given day is very high or very low, then that day is consid-
88 ered extreme. For example, (Messori et al., 2024) define extremes as exceeding the per-
89 centile threshold (e.g. 95) at specific grid points. A subsequent clustering step is used
90 to determine the spatial extent of heatwaves or cold spells. Similarly, (Yin et al., 2025)
91 present a method that combines percentile-based thresholds with absolute criteria (e.g.
92 days over a certain temperature) to identify compound events. Different strategies are
93 employed to manage seasonality and mitigate potential biases (Brunner & Voigt, 2024).

94 Any event evolves in its own way and is, in principle, attributable to a unique set
95 of drivers (Stott et al., 2016). Many studies assume prior knowledge about the time and
96 spatial extent of each anomalous event, resulting in a strong dependency of each detec-
97 tion method on its event type. For instance, to assess whether a given trend or event is
98 statistically attributable to global warming, the first steps often include fixing the spa-
99 tial and temporal definition of the given event and the parameters to be analyzed (Eden
100 et al., 2016, 2018; Otto et al., 2023; Zachariah et al., 2023). Chosen physical param-
101 eters are usually the most extreme and abnormal ones (Philip et al., 2020), and attribu-
102 tion of an event requires a generalized ability to identify anomalies in any variables that
103 might influence an event (Stott et al., 2016).

104 Understanding how specific climate anomalies propagate over space is also crucial
105 for predicting where and when resulting disasters may occur. Many tracking approaches
106 have been employed to analyze propagation in various climate impact sectors including
107 (but not limited to) tropical cyclones (Knutson et al., 2019), storms, floods, or flash droughts
108 (J. Li et al., 2020). Related studies usually address these issues by detecting spatial pat-
109 terns that describe spatial boundaries of the given anomalous event. Such detection meth-
110 ods often use spatio-temporal clustering approaches such as connected components (Tilloy
111 et al., 2022), then show how related spatial clusters evolve in time and space by iden-
112 tifying close events or behaviors occurring simultaneously.

113 In this study, we introduce *ClimBurst*, a new method to detect intervals of climate
114 anomalies (hereafter *climate bursts*) of any unanticipated duration and for any climate-
115 related variable (e.g. temperature, precipitation). *ClimBurst* here distinguishes from pre-
116 vious work starting from daily extremes, as it detects extreme bursts that may exist over
117 long durations, i.e. even when no single day is extreme. We apply our method to one
118 case study, and detect bursts over daily Sea Surface Temperatures (SST) from 1960 to
119 2021 over the Mediterranean sea.

2 Material and Methods

2.1 *Climate Bursts to Detect Climate Anomalies*

In this study, a *burst* (or climate burst) is defined as a time interval starting in a given year y whose accumulated values are unusually high or low for a given climate variable (e.g. $+5^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature anomaly from July 3 to July 16, 2004) compared to the same time period in all years. Our approach identifies bursts over all possible time intervals, regardless of their duration or season, enabling the detection of short events (e.g. a 3-day burst in April of some year) as well as longer anomalies (e.g. a 15-day burst from December 26 of year y to January 10 of year $y + 1$).

Computationally, a burst is characterized by its z-score (similarly to the SPI (Tsakiris & Vangelis, 2005)) that quantifies the relative position of an individual data point within a distribution. This score represents the number of standard deviations by which a data point deviates from the mean of the distribution. The higher the absolute z-score value of a data point, the more anomalous it is. We use z-score instead of percentiles for the following reason: with percentiles, for every month-day there will be one or more years which have a high percentile on that month-day and at least one or more years which are low on that month-day. With z-scores, there will be many month-days without any year having a z-score over some bound. For example, a uniform distribution of temperatures will have no values whose z-scores fall above 2 or below -2. Thus, using the z-score allows us to detect events that are really extreme, not just those that lie in the tail of the distribution.

The z-score is calculated using the well-known formula (Larsen & Marx, 2005):

$$z = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}$$

where z is the z-score, x the observed data value (e.g. the sum of the temperatures over a certain date range), μ the mean of the distribution (e.g. of sums), and σ the standard deviation.

As an illustrative climate example, the z-score of rainfall in Dakar over a certain time interval (e.g. July 8 to July 23) of a certain year (e.g. 2004) would be the z-score of the total rainfall over that period in Dakar based on the total rainfall in Dakar between July 8 to July 23 in each year on record. The z-score provides a contextual measure of abnormality based on the typical values over the date range. This reflects the fact that the severity of an anomaly is often contextual.

Overview of ClimBurst algorithm. For all interval lengths within a user-defined range (e.g., 3 to 90 days), ClimBurst:

- Computes the cumulative value (e.g., sum of temperature) for every interval;
- For each calendar interval (defined by starting and ending month-dates), gathers values from the same calendar period across all years in the dataset;
- Computes the mean and standard deviation for that calendar-specific distribution;
- Calculates the z-score of the interval value relative to the distribution of that calendar period across years;
- Returns intervals whose z-scores exceed a user-defined positive or negative z-score threshold (e.g., ± 3).

Although computing bursts across all intervals length (duration) might seem computationally expensive, we provide an algorithm that does it quickly. For example, for a 64-year time series of daily temperature data, with an absolute z-score threshold of 3, we find all bursts of duration 1 to 365 in under 50ms on a conventional laptop [Intel i9-

166 13900H@2.6GHz]. Further algorithmic details are available in Supporting Information
 167 (see Text S1).

168 Given that we can identify climate bursts of any duration, some of these may be
 169 included in, or exhibit a high level of overlap with one another. This leads to a consid-
 170 erable degree of redundancy. We merge them into continuous sequences, forming a *Merged*
 171 *Burst Representation* (e.g. merging overlapping bursts from July 3–16 and July 10–19
 172 into a single event spanning July 3–19). This process takes under 10ms for a single time
 173 series on the same hardware platform.

174 **2.2 Climate Bursts and Spatial Extents: Connected Components**

175 In this study, we combine burst detection at individual grid cells with connected
 176 component analysis to identify patterns of neighboring bursts and how they evolve in
 177 time and space. This makes it possible to differentiate between small-scale anomalies (e.g.
 178 local rainfall event) and larger-scale processes (e.g. seasonal monsoon) (C. Li et al., 2019).

179 After applying the burst detection algorithm to each grid cell, ClimBurst computes
 180 connected components based on spatio-temporal adjacency of the bursts. Specifically,
 181 a burst in one grid cell is considered adjacent to another if: i) the two grid cells are ad-
 182 jacent in space using a 8-neighbor connectivity, ii) their burst time intervals have at least
 183 one overlapping day.

184 **2.3 Case study on Sea Surface Temperatures (SST) in the Mediterranean** 185 **sea**

186 ClimBurst can be applied to any spatial scale (global to local) and on any climate-
 187 related variables. This paper presents a case study on one variable and one dataset to
 188 illustrate how the method can be used and what information can be extracted. We ap-
 189 ply ClimBurst to daily non-detrended Sea Surface Temperature (SST) from the fifth-
 190 generation reanalysis produced by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) at the
 191 European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF), hereafter ERA5. This
 192 dataset combines model data with global-scale observations (i.e. data assimilation) into
 193 a consistent and complete climate dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020).

194 We focus on SST over the Mediterranean Sea (coordinates: 30°N to 46°N, –5°E
 195 to 36°E) and apply our method on the regional averaged SST. As ClimBurst can detect
 196 all z-scores bursts, here we display and describe main results based on bursts with an
 197 absolute z-score value greater than 3 (see more z-score thresholds in Figure S1). We ar-
 198 gue such z-score value of 3 is a commonly used value to detect outliers with z-score meth-
 199 ods (Iglewicz & Hoaglin, 1993). In this paper, positive z-score values correspond to *hot/warm*
 200 anomalies while negative values correspond to *cold* anomalies. For this paper, we also
 201 only consider events of small (1 day) to medium (3 months) temporal duration for sim-
 202 plification purpose, but please note that ClimBurst is not limited to these scales.

203 **3 Results**

204 **3.1 Regional averaged SST bursts within the Mediterranean Sea**

205 On the average SST calculated over the Mediterranean sea, we identify five distinct
 206 bursts of varying duration in 2001, 2015, 2016, and two in 2018 (Figure 1a). These bursts
 207 represent statistical anomalies when compared to the same date ranges between 1960 and
 208 2021. These climate bursts range from short events lasting 2-4 days in 2015 and 2018,
 209 to longer ones of 15 and 30 days in 2016 and 2001, respectively, and three of these five
 210 bursts are detected during spring (Figure 1a). Since the anomalies are calculated over

211 the entire averaged Mediterranean basin, they detect large scale events, such as the severe
 212 marine heatwave of 2015 (Darmaraki et al., 2019).

213 Our climate burst approach can also provide daily absolute maximum z-scores in-
 214 formation. Since a single day can belong to intervals of varying durations with differ-
 215 ent z-score values, we assign to each day the highest absolute z-score among those in-
 216 tervals. This reveals how the highest intensities of bursts are distributed across years.
 217 We display such information similarly as a Hovmöller diagram (Figure 1b). Along the
 218 dates of a year, the daily values exhibit various maximum z-score values across years,
 219 with the five highest values for SST in 2001, 2015, 2016, and 2018 (consistent with Fig-
 220 ure 1a). This diagram also reveals how this method detects particular long hot events
 221 (e.g. hot SSTs during the extended summer in 2003) while z-scores are not the highest.
 222 Consistently with the literature (Nykjaer, 2009), corresponding burst have intensified
 223 and are predominantly positive (hot) up to 2021, with no negative (cold) anomalies since
 224 the winter of 2008.

225 Figure 1c shows the z-score distribution for the year 2001 for exponentially increas-
 226 ing numbers of days (see more years in Figure S2). In this figure, we illustrate intervals
 227 whose durations (in days) are powers of two (arbitrarily chosen for visual simplicity) and
 228 calculate their z-scores. In the example, the highest z-score bursts are detected at the
 229 end of March 2001 (black lines show z-scores above +3). These bursts seem to be included
 230 in a longer 32-day scale anomaly in March-April with a lower yet still elevated z-score.
 231 The exponential analysis enables the detection of climate-related anomalies covering mul-
 232 tiple time scales. This shows the linkage between short time-scale events and long time-
 233 scale anomalies.

234 3.2 Spatio-temporal Connected Bursts (CB)

235 We illustrate a specific detected spatio-temporal anomalous event lasting from 17
 236 April 2013 to 27 May 2013 to describe characteristics of such detected connected burst
 237 (Fig. 2a, see more examples from Figure S3 to S6 in SI). To capture the evolution of the
 238 connected component’s spatial extent, we define the density as the ratio of grid points
 239 with active bursts on a given day to the total grid points in the connected component.
 240 In the given example, the density begins to rise on April 22nd (Fig. 2b) and peaks around
 241 May 3rd reaching 90% of the total number of grid points in the connected component.
 242 Spatially, the points containing the highest number of days belonging to bursts (≥ 30
 243 days) are concentrated near the center of the pattern which is west of Crete (Fig. 2c).
 244 Points having approximately 20 burst days are near the west and south-east of Greece,
 245 and the points with approximately 5-10 burst days are located near the edges of the con-
 246 nected component (Fig. 2c). Figure 2d shows that the event started in the connected
 247 component center on April 17th, and then propagated north-westward and eastward in
 248 the following days. The grid points furthest from the center are the bursts that started
 249 the latest and stopped the earliest (Fig. 2d, 2e). The latest occurrence within the pat-
 250 tern is the localized center near the West of Crete, which has the highest total number
 251 of burst days (Fig. 2e and 2c).

252 ClimBurst here enables the capture and detailed description of the spatio-temporal
 253 evolution and propagation of climate-related anomalous events, regardless of their in-
 254 tensity, spatial extent, or time duration. As a complement to the connected component
 255 approach, we illustrate corresponding examples of *time travel* videos published on Github
 256 (<https://github.com/GuillaumeCld/ClimBurst>, see the Open Research Section). This
 257 visualization displays day-by-day and grid-by-grid information about this same climate
 258 event for illustration purposes.

Figure 1: **Detected bursts in SST over the Mediterranean sea during the 1960-2021 period.** (a) Seasonal cycles of averaged Mediterranean Sea Surface Temperature (SST) during 1960-2021 and detected bursts (colored lines) with absolute z-score value above 3. Each color indicates a particular year in which a burst occurred; (b) Heatmap of daily maximal z-scores over 30 years. Positive (hot) bursts are displayed in red whereas negative (cold) bursts are shown in blue; (c) Exponentially scale day duration (based on powers of 2) visualization of z-scores for 2001.

(a) Connected component of the April-May 2013 event

(b) Density over time

(c) Number of days per grid cell

(d) First date per grid cell

(e) Last date per grid cell

Figure 2: **Spatio-temporal connected bursts (CB) related characteristics: example of an event detected in April-May 2013.** (a) Spatial extent of the CB example; (b) Density (fraction of grid cells) in the CB that exceeded the z-score threshold of 3 over time; (c) Number of days per grid cell within the CB with a z-score of at least 3; (d) First date per grid cell being included in the CB; (e) Last date per grid cell being included in the CB.

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3.3 Trends of connected bursts over 1960-2021

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Here we investigate time evolution of detected connected SST bursts between 1960 and 2021 within the Mediterranean Sea (Figures 3, S7 and S8). We show that the total number of days included in a warm (cold) burst with z-score above (below) 3 (-3) significantly increases (decreases) over time between 1960 and 2021. Only a few days with hot bursts are found at the beginning of the 1960s followed by cold bursts from 1970 to 2000, and an increasing number of warm burst days from the early 2000s until 2021 (Fig. 3a). Accordingly, the spatial extent (expressed in percentage of the number of grid cells over the number of all grid cells with at least one warm burst day per year) increases (Fig. 3b). The method also shows that the cold burst spatial extent rarely exceeds 20%, whereas hot burst extent exceeds 20% most of the time after 2000.

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The combined information regarding the four main averaged characteristics (spatial extent, duration, frequency of occurrence and intensity) of connected bursts (CB) are displayed per year in the form of bubble plots (Ouzeau et al., 2016)). For the sake of visual clarity, we have removed events lasting less than 4 days or covering less than 1% of the grid. Over the Mediterranean Sea, days and grid cell numbers included in a warm CB have both increased (Figure 3c). Consistently, only few cold CB are detected from 2008 on (Figure 3c).

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Trends are explored over the 1960-2021 period (Figures S7 and S8). Calculated trends over the period 1994–2021 indicate an increase of 2.24 hot CB events per decade, a rise of 1.75 days per decade in their duration, an intensification of 0.16°K per decade in their temperature anomaly (intensity), and an expansion of 0.56 grid cells per decade in their average spatial extent (Figure S7a-c-e-g, Figure S8). Consistently, cold CB features have decreased (Figure S7b-d-f-h). Our results are consistent with existing literature showing an observed mean warming of $+0.4^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{decade}$ in the Mediterranean Sea (Cherif et al., 2020). Our detected burst results are also consistent with detected strong marine heatwaves that occurred during the 2010s in the region (Darmaraki et al., 2019).

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3.4 Hotspots of the Starting Points of Connected Bursts

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As an example of a possible use of *ClimBurst*, we investigate where warm spatial anomalies originate. To do this, for each connected component, we identify the grid cells whose burst begins in the first few days of the component. Two relative (quantile) thresholds of starting dates are represented in Figure 4 (first 5% days and first 20%). Heatmaps of all burst onsets of warm SST connected components reveal several localized hotspots (Fig. 4). The figure shows that the Adriatic Sea, the Aegean Sea, and the Central Mediterranean are characterized by 6 to 8 hot connected component onsets. Literature has revealed that the maximum SST increase ($+0.16^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{year}$) is found close to the African coast, in the Tyrrhenian, Ligurian, Adriatic, and Aegean Seas (Nykjaer, 2009). *ClimBurst* detected hotspots of onsets consistently with the literature except for in the Aegean and Adriatic seas, suggesting that local SST warm anomalies in those places are less related to the observed Mediterranean warming than warming in other locations.

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4 Conclusions and Discussion

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This study has introduced the *ClimBurst* method as a novel framework for identifying and analyzing anomalies in individual grid points of any time duration. Through an extension based on connected components, we demonstrated its analytical insights over space as well as time.

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We have illustrated the analytical utility of the method by applying it to Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data from the Mediterranean Sea (1960–2021) obtained from the ERA5 dataset. Our results showcase the ability of *ClimBurst* to detect contextual

Figure 3: Evolution of cold and hot SST bursts (absolute z-score above 3) within the Mediterranean Sea between 1960 and 2021. (a) Timeseries in the form of histogram of the aggregated number of days belonging to bursts per year for all grid cells. (b) Timeseries in the form of histogram of percentage of grid cells containing at least one burst day per year; (c) Bubble plots of the evolution of connected bursts (CB) features. Each bubble gives combined information of the year of occurrence (x-axis), the duration (y-axis), the spatial extent (bubble size), and the averaged CB temperature anomaly. If there are several bubbles in the same year, then there are several connected components in that year.

Figure 4: Heatmaps illustrating how many times a pixel is characterized as the first day of a climate burst with a z-score greater than 3 during 1960-2021. The relative threshold indicates the threshold to consider to select the first days of a connected component, here 5% in (a) and 20% in (b).

307 anomalies at various time scales and varying intensities (z-scores), independently of sea-
 308 sonal patterns. For example, anomalies are identified in both spring and summer. Warm
 309 SST anomalies align with known marine heatwaves in the region. Furthermore, we show
 310 that ClimBurst can track the spatio-temporal evolution of anomalies, identify their ap-
 311 proximate local starting point, and analyze regional trends over the study period. This
 312 includes describing the evolution of the anomalies' features (spatial extent, duration, fre-
 313 quency).

314 Because climate bursts are contextual in that they are based on date ranges within
 315 a specific year range, they should be interpreted with caution. Anomalies with compa-
 316 rable z-scores across disparate time periods may differ significantly in terms of causes
 317 or impact. For example, hot anomalies in winter and early spring can result in more abrupt
 318 and earlier snow recession in some regions, whereas heat events in spring and summer
 319 mostly induce increased wildfire frequency and severity (Collow et al., 2022). ClimBurst
 320 thus should be explored and applied to other datasets, variables, and timescales, but this
 321 will not always be straightforward. For instance, when analyzing rainfall data, cumu-
 322 lative values for short intervals may be zero in the majority of years and non-zero in a
 323 few due to the inherently strong day-to-day variability (Sivakumar, 2001). In such cases,
 324 z-scores may erroneously classify non-zero intervals as outliers, potentially leading to false
 325 discoveries. These situations may thus require special-purpose post-processing such as
 326 focusing only on intervals above a certain number of days for rainfall.

327 Alternatively, percentile-based approaches, which are distribution-independent, may
 328 be more appropriate for highly skewed variables like precipitation. These methods evalu-
 329 ate extremeness based on rank rather than deviation from the mean, and may reduce
 330 the likelihood of false positives when the distribution is non-Gaussian (Messori et al., 2024).
 331 However, because ClimBurst compares intervals of fixed length and calendar date across
 332 multiple years, some of these small-sample distributions may lack a meaningful notion
 333 of extremeness, making percentile cutoffs less informative in certain cases. Future work
 334 might indeed explore integrating percentile-based analysis into ClimBurst, although spe-
 335 cial care must be taken to avoid false positives.

336 The connected components approach may link spatio-temporal anomalies into large
 337 components that contain distinct smaller-scale anomalies. While this offers a compre-
 338 hensive perspective of interconnected phenomena, it may also link disparate or unrelated
 339 time series. Such issues should be explored in further studies to possibly classify anomaly

340 types (e.g. disparate vs connected broad anomalies) when using ClimBurst. The results
 341 can serve as a step toward event detection in attribution studies, where a generalized and
 342 systematic approach for event detection is often lacking (Van Der Wiel et al., 2017; Van Old-
 343 enborgh et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2023). This is particularly important when investigat-
 344 ing whether a given event or trend is more or less probable due to human-induced global
 345 warming.

346 Open Research Section

347 The sea surface temperature data are obtained from the ERA5 hourly data from
 348 the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S, 2018). We make the *ClimBurst* method
 349 available as an open-source code. The code consists of Jupyter notebooks with Python
 350 code to display the visualizations of the paper including year-duration-extent bubble plots,
 351 connected component evolutions, and time travel videos to visualize the temporal evo-
 352 lution of bursts at the grid or at a connected component level. The code is licensed un-
 353 der CeCILL and published on GitHub <https://github.com/GuillaumeCld/ClimBurst>.
 354 The GitHub also includes the averaged time series and the script to pre-process the grid.

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